

**VISUAL CONCEPTS OF CONTEMPORARY MAGAZINES AND SIGNIFICANCE OF DESIGN
COVERS IN MAGAZINE MARKETING STRUCTURE****(magazines "Teatri", "Arili", "ARTFORUM", "Art in America")****Asmat Tsereteli***A PhD student of the doctoral program Mass communication,
Caucasus International University***Abstract**

Media and culture play a pivotal role in shaping public consciousness. Over the years, cultural tastes have been shaped by a complex interplay of social factors, including peer influence. Media has expanded this influence exponentially, creating a new cultural landscape.

Cultural journalism plays a crucial role in fostering an informed and democratic society. In conjunction with the field of culture, it provides the public with essential information to make informed decisions. The degree of societal trust in the media is contingent upon several factors, including the media's independence from governmental and other external influences, its capacity for critical thinking and analysis, its willingness to address open-ended questions, its commitment to verifying information, and its ability to present a range of perspectives and draw logical conclusions. The media's ability to comfort society is contingent upon its adherence to principles of truth, objectivity, impartiality, and promptness. The development of society is inextricably linked to the quality of the media.

The objective of our research is to examine the representation of cultural topics in Georgian and American print media, with a particular focus on two Georgian and two American magazines. The periodicals "**Teatri**," "**Arili**," "**ARTFORUM**," and "**Art in America**" were selected for analysis. This paper will examine the discourse diversity of art in media, with a particular focus on the visual concepts employed in contemporary magazines and the role of the cover in the marketing structures of the aforementioned magazines.

Keywords: media, culture, cover, contemporary magazines, visual concepts

Introduction

As is the case for the entire world, culture and art are significant domains for Georgia. These fields facilitate the intellectual, political, and economic advancement of the nation, and elucidating these subjects has consistently been a pertinent endeavor.

The **relevance** of our paper is determined by the object of our study, namely Georgian and American art magazines. In order to ascertain the relevance of our study, it is necessary to consider the contextual aspects as well as the visual concepts inherent to these magazines.

With regard to the **novelty of research**, this represents the first attempt to undertake a comparative analysis of Georgian and American art magazines, utilizing print media materials.

In this article, we employ the **content analysis** research method and the **contrastive analysis** to examine the visual concepts and impact of cover designs in Georgian and American magazines.

Magazines that are successful in terms of their circulation and revenue streams endeavour to respond in a creative manner to current events. This is evident not only in the content that they publish but also in the design of their covers and the visual concepts that they employ. In light of the accelerated pace of contemporary events, magazine editors frequently encounter the challenge of producing covers at the last minute. The cover serves as a powerful visual identifier for a magazine, making it imperative to create designs that are both striking and memorable. While editorial content is of the utmost importance, commercial considerations must also be taken into account when designing a cover. In certain instances, specific events

or individuals may be perceived as particularly newsworthy or commercially relevant at a given moment in time. From the perspective of the photographer, magazine covers convey visual impressions that resonate with readers.

This article will examine the visual concepts employed in research magazines, with a particular focus on the role of the cover as an "introductory word." The most fundamental element of any publication bearing the brand logo is the cover. The cover is the element of the publication that should convey the publication's attitude in an immediately apparent manner. This distinguishes it from other specific magazines. In his book, *Newspaper Design*, Harold Evans, editor of *The Sunday Times*, observed that the printed media is a conduit for the conveyance of ideas, and design is an integral component of that process (Evans, 1981).

The effective application of visual journalism, photography, and infographics is a vital component of the success of any magazine. Cover designs can be broadly categorized into three principal types: figurative, abstract, and text-based. Our research indicates that both figurative and abstract covers are employed in academic journals, but text-based covers remain the most prevalent format.

The magazine "Teatri" adheres to a consistent visual and editorial style. Its cover designs are closely aligned with the thematic content of each issue. Besik Danelia is the publication's designer. For illustrative purposes, one may cite the November 2019 issue, which features a portrait of Dante Alighieri, drawn by Sergo Kobuladze, which complements the issue's thematic focus. A portrait essay "A barcode of Kobuladze" by Davit Andriadze is presented in the "Vernissage"

section. Sergo Kobuladze, whose creative methodology demonstrates an affinity with graphic and dynamic principles, frequently draws inspiration from the historical development of art. His adroitness in the use of a pencil to portray Dante Alighieri serves to exemplify this approach.” (Andriadze, 2019).

To commemorate its 110th anniversary in 2020, i.e. the magazine was founded in 1910, it featured the cover of its January 1, 1918 issue (magazine “Teatri da Tskhovreba, in *English*: “*Theatre and Life*”) on one of its own covers. In the same issue, Levan Bregadze's article, “When Art Spreads Its Wings”, is thematically related to the cover. In this article, the author makes the following observation: “Founded in 1910 by Ioseb Imedashvili, “Theatre and Life” magazine featured a distinctive cover design. The upper portion of the cover, which remained consistent across issues, displayed the magazine's title and theatrical symbols. The lower portion, however, was variable, showcasing images of writers, actors, or artistic groups.” (Bregadze, 2020).

As Austrian writer Arthur Schnitzler observed, the ultimate objective of all culture is to render politics obsolete and to establish science and art as indispensable to humanity. The cover of the fourth 2020 issue of “Teatri” magazine features a photograph of Julian Roeder from Susan Kennedy and Markus Selg's play *Future Society*. Furthermore, the same issue includes Sofia Tortladze's “Berlin Diaries” in the “Fiesta” section, in which the author discusses the performance and its connection to contemporary German theater. Furthermore, it challenges Arthur Schnitzler's assertion that culture should render politics obsolete by examining the concept of the *Volksbühne*. The latter denotes a cultural society that has been cultivated by a political idea (Tortladze, 2020). The covers of various issues feature works by artists such as Anselm Kiefer, Kazimir Malevich, Paul Klee, Nicholas Mirisch, Rezo Gabriadze, and Felix Varlamishvili.

The distinctive cover designs of “Arili” magazine are the consequence of a collaborative endeavour between the editorial team and cover designer Mamuka Tkeshelashvili. The cover of the fifth 2019 issue of Arili features a photograph of the equestrian statue of Roman Emperor Marcus Aurelius, which serves as a thematic complement to Joseph Brodsky's essay “In Honor of Marcus Aurelius”, also included in the issue.

The magazine “Arili” introduced Georgian readers to a diverse range of international authors through high-quality translations. Among these authors was Peter Handke, the Austrian writer, playwright, translator, film director, and screenwriter who was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature in 2019 for his significant contributions to the literary world. The cover of the seventh 2019 issue of “Arili” features a pencil portrait of Handke. This issue also includes a translation of his short story, “Das Umfallen der Kegel von einer bäuerlichen Kegelbahn” translated from German into Georgian by Natia Datuashvili.

The falling of the pins from a rural bowling alley The covers of the sixth 2021 and eighth 2022 issues of “Arili” feature portraits of Nobel laureates Louise Glück and Annie Ernaux, respectively. The

magazine consistently publishes their work, which often addresses feminist themes and social issues.

In 1962, the American art magazine ARTFORUM was established by John Irwin Jr. Philip Leider was the initial artist to contribute to the magazine, suggesting to Irwin that he should begin to promote local artists and the West Coast School of Art. With the assistance of Pisani Printing Company and editorial oversight from Irvine, the first issue of the magazine was successfully published. The cover was designed by the Swiss artist Jean Tinguely. The current designer and production manager of ARTFORUM is Tina Tran. From July 24 to August 23, 2019, the majority of issues from the 1962 period of ARTFORUM were presented at the Sotheby's New York exhibition in New York. The exhibition was met with considerable interest from art critics, who not only discussed the content of the magazine but also the visual concepts behind its design, including the cover. The cover of the magazine was evaluated as a prospective representation of the evolution of modern art.

The September 2022 issue of “Arili” featured the work of Colombian artist Delcy Morelos. His philosophy, rooted in Andean traditions, posits a deep connection between humanity and the earth. The artist's work, showcased on the magazine's cover, embodies this concept, portraying the earth as both a physical and spiritual center. “In Andean ancestral traditions, the human being is living earth, I am a body, I am earth. In the exhibition space, the earth expresses itself; it is the center and mirror of what we are” (Morelos, 2022). This work by Colombian artist Delcy Morelos, along with his philosophical vision, was featured on the cover of the September 2022 issue of the magazine. Morelos' practice draws inspiration from a synthesis of Andean cosmology and minimalist art aesthetics. The practice of this talented artist has its roots in the cosmic and Andean traditions, as well as in the principles of minimalist art aesthetics. “ARTFORUM” has a particular focus on publishing the works of women artists who are actively engaged in the field. The fifth issue of the magazine, published in 2023, features the work of Brazilian artist Marina Reinganz, renowned for her semi-abstract landscape paintings. The artist's compositions, characterized by a rich chromatic palette, explore the boundaries between abstraction and figuration, evoking a sense of imaginary space.

The cover design and visual concepts of the magazine *Art in America* are worthy of note for their intriguing nature. The August 2023 issue features a striking image of a woman with a pit bull against a red background. This artwork serves as a contemporary protest against global conflicts, particularly the ongoing wars in Ukraine and Gaza. This period, much like the interwar years of the 20th century, has inspired artists to turn to surrealism to express the horrors of war. While some magazine covers may prioritize commercial considerations, the overall aesthetic of this publication aligns with international art trends and showcases the work of contemporary artists.

Conclusion

This article examines the visual concepts and cover design strategies employed by Georgian and

American magazines – “Teatri”, “Arili”, “ARTFORUM” and “Art in America”. In the current, highly competitive environment of magazine publishing, marketing represents a critical element in ensuring the financial viability and sustainability of individual titles. While the cover serves as a powerful marketing tool, it also functions as a first impression, influencing the reader's initial perception of the publication.

In contrast to the Georgian publishing industry, which often prioritizes the mere act of survival, the American industry is more reader-centric. Every aspect of magazine production, from the design of the cover to that of the interior layout, is planned and executed with great care and attention to detail. Major publishers, who invest considerable resources in cover design, even when more cost-effective alternatives are available, recognize the essential function of the cover in both marketing and content. The cover is the primary visual identifier for a publication.

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